

New Approach for Encryption Private key for Sender by using Hill Cipher with GGH Cryptography

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Abstract—One of the important issues in the encryption used in networks is the Hill encryption method, but it is not practical in economic matters or the Internet, It is very difficult to send the private key to the receive in order to decrypt the message, due to the high exposure to third-party attacks, and therefore it is recommended that the private key must be encrypted before sending it to the receive and the receive will try to decrypt the private key by the way GGH algorithm in order to obtain the real key for decrypting the message Hill's method.

In this case, one of the Lattice algorithms was used to provide a strong bond for the Hill cipher .One of these important algorithms is GGH cryptosystem.

Keywords-component; encryption ;GGH, Hill cipher; Lattice

I. INTRODUCTION

Hill Cipher is a symmetric block cipher technique invented by mathematician Lester Hill (1891-1961) in 1929[1]. It is a multi-line encryption based on linear transformation. Hill cipher is a block cipher algorithm where the plain text is split into blocks of the same size[2,3].

In Hill cipher, the key is block size of with a size of $n \times n$ where n =block size is a non-singular matrix [1]. Both the sender and receiver must share and use the same key of matrix for encryption and description[4].

Each letter is represented on a scale of the number 26. Although this is not a primary feature of encryption , this simple scheme is often used [5].

Letter	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T	U	V	W	X	Y	Z
Number	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25

To encryption a message, each block of n characters (considered a vector n component) is multiplied by an inverted $n \times n$ matrix, against the modulus of parameter 26. To decrypt of the message, each block is multiplied by the inverse of the matrix used in the encryption [6,7].

The matrix used for encryption is the encryption key, and should be randomly selected from the set of inverse $n \times n$ matrices (scale 26). The code, of course, can be adapted to the alphabet with any number of characters [8].All math operations only need to be performed on a character count rather than on a scale of 26 .

II. ENCRYPTION BY HILL CIPHER

Encrypts n plaintext letters to n cipher text letters[9,10]

• For $n=3$, let the plaintext be $P = (P_1, P_2, P_3)$ and the cipher text be $C = (C_1, C_2, C_3)$

• For encryption

• $C = K P \text{ mod } 26$, where C is the cipher text matrix, K is the key matrix and P is the plaintext matrix

• Decryption uses the inverse of K : Then

• $P = K^{-1}C \text{ mod } 26$ (where $KK^{-1} = I$ the identity matrix I)

• The system can be described as a set of linear equations

•Decoding using frequency analysis is challenging, especially with an increase in the size of n . this is

•The encryption hides the single-character frequencies, as well as the digram, trigram, etc., even $(n-1)$ - grams, for length n to any chosen block .

• Hence, the Hill cipher is powerful against text only attack.

• However, it falls easily (in most cases) into a well-known plain text attack [11].

III. GGH cryptosystem

The GGH encoder system is designed to be a new encoding and decoding mechanism based on the hardness of the CVP solution[12].

It always motivates us to enter encryption systems based on many difficult mathematical problems, thus highly confidential information encoded by more than one algorithm remains safe even if part of it is broken. Network-based encryption systems are born with many advantages, for example, they offer encryption and decoding much faster than encryption systems based on separate logarithms and large number factors. Besides, the matrix operations feature makes GGH coding system easier to implement in hardware and software of modems compared to RSA and ElGamal [13].

A. BASIC DEFINITION

The Goldreich - Goldwasser - Halevi (GGH) coding system takes advantage of the fact that the closest vector problem can be a challenging one. This system was published in 1997 by Oded Goldreich, Shafi Goldwasser, and Shai Halevi, and it uses a one-way trapdoor function that relies on the difficulty of reducing the network. The idea embedded in this Trapdoor function is that, in light of any network foundation, it is easy to create a vector close to a lattice point, for example taking a lattice point and adding a small error vector. But to return from this faulty vector to the original network point, a special basis is needed [13,14].

To start the GGH cryptosystem, Alice creates a private key as shown an equation (1), which will be kept secret throughout the entire information exchange. In order to achieve this, you choose an integer matrix for an entire column:

$$V = [v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n] (v_i \in \mathbb{Z}^n, 1 \leq i \leq n) \dots \dots (1)$$

The columns in V are reasonably orthogonal to each other, which can be verified by calculating Hadamard's ratio of matrix V. Alice then chooses this matrix V as her private key[15].

Suppose L is the lattice generated by the columns of matrix V. Then Alice randomly generates an n-by-n integer of the un modular matrix U, which checks $\det(U) = \pm 1$

To create the single-modular U matrix, Alice can randomly generate a series of prime matrices and multiply them together. Then a new matrix W can be constructed by computing $W = VU$, and W^{-1} It is easy to discover. Continue to Alice a file account Matrix an integer W iteratively until Hadamard's ratio to W is small enough. Then the correct matrix W can be selected as the public key and published to the public. According to W is another generator matrix of the lattice L.

B. ENCRYPTION PROCESS

Plain text m of GGH is an integer vector with the same dimension, and that agrees Lattice L. Bob encodes the plain text m with the public key W. A small perturbation integer vector r called an ephemeral key will be added to the encoder Vector at the same time as shown an equation (2). Geometrically, the Euclidean length of r should be less From half of the shortest distance to any two adjacent points in L. Thus, Plain text m is then encoded into an unencrypted integer ciphertext vector Belong to the Lattice of Lattice[14,16].

$$e = W m + r \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

For some chosen m, the message space consists of the (m_1, m_2, \dots, m_n) , r is vector noise W public key of basis lattice.

C. DECRYPTION PROCESS

Decoding the cipher text e is straightforward. Alice uses her private key V to find the closest v vector to the cipher text vector e by the BABAI algorithm. To discover the original m plain text by equations (3) and (4), Alice can simply compute it using the public key W in the formula below.

$$e = t_1 v_1 + t_2 v_2 \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

Now find t_1, t_2 parameters as a round operation $\text{Round}(t_1) * v_1 + \text{round}(t_2) * v_2 =$ encryption before add r vector noise

Encryption before add r vector noise

$$= m_1 W_1 + m_2 W_2 \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

And by the equation (4) to find plain text $m = (m_1, m_2, \dots)$

IV. Algorithm Research

Step 1 : : ENCRYPTION PROCESS

Start

INPUT: 1. Public key w_1, w_2, \dots for GGH

2. $r =$ vector noise $-10 \leq r_x, r_y \dots \leq 10$

3. private key k for sender to Hill Cipher

Begin

For two dimension example:

$Dp1 =$ key private $k(1) * w_1 +$ key private $k(1) * w_2;$

$Dp2 =$ key private $k(2) * w_1 +$ key private $k(2) * w_2;$

encryption foe private key for hill cipher= $c1 = Dp1 + r;$
 $c2 = Dp2 + r;$

end

output

encryption for private key for Hill cipher

end

Step 2 : : DECRYPTION PROCESS

Start

INPUT: 1. Public key w_1, w_2, \dots for GGH

2. Private key v_1, v_2, \dots for GGH

3. Encryption for private key from Sender by Hill cipher and GGH

Begin
 $V=[v1;v2];$
 $W=[w1;w2];$
 $tnew1 = c1*Inverse \text{ for } V$
 $Gg1=tnew1(1)*v1+tnew1(2)*v1;$
 $Ggh1 =round(Gg1* inv(W));$
 $tnew2 = c2*Inverse \text{ for } V$
 $Gg2=tnew2(1)*v1+tnew2(2)*v2;$
 $Ggh2 =round(Gg2*inv(W));$
 decryption for private key from the sender for Hill cipher
 ::Ggh1 ,Ggh2
 Output
 decryption for private key from the sender for Hill cipher
 end

V. MEASUREMENT AND CALCULATION

First :Hill Cipher

$$K = \begin{bmatrix} 3 & 3 \\ 2 & 5 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\det(K) = 9$$

$$P = SU, \text{ this is represented by } \begin{bmatrix} S \\ U \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow \begin{bmatrix} 18 \\ 20 \end{bmatrix}$$

To encrypt t ,compute

$$C = KP = \begin{bmatrix} 3 & 3 \\ 2 & 5 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 18 \\ 20 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 114 \\ 130 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 10 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \pmod{26} = \begin{bmatrix} K \\ G \end{bmatrix}$$

To decrypt, find

$$\det(K)^{-1} =$$

$$9^{-1} = 3 \pmod{26}$$

$$K^{-1} = \det(K)^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} 5 & -3 \\ -2 & 3 \end{bmatrix} = 3 \begin{bmatrix} 5 & 23 \\ 24 & 3 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 10 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \pmod{26}$$

Finally,

$$\text{compute } P = K^{-1}C = \begin{bmatrix} 3 & 188 \\ 3 & 238 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 364 \\ 774 \end{bmatrix} \pmod{26} = \begin{bmatrix} S \\ U \end{bmatrix}$$

Second: Sender

We have a private key:

$$K = \begin{bmatrix} 3 & 3 \\ 2 & 5 \end{bmatrix}$$

We will make this key in two parts as follows:

$$M1=[3 \ 3], M2=[2 \ 5]$$

Using an algorithm GGH , we will encrypt the private key and send it to the recipient, as follows :

Public key : $w1=[226 \ 40], w2=[1853 \ 319]$, and vector noise is
 $r=(rx ,ry)=[-9 \ 2]$

Provided condition that it values between: $-10 \leq rx ,ry \leq 10$

$$Dp1=3w1+3w1$$

$$Dp2=2w1+5w2$$

The add dp1 ,dp2 with r

$$C1=Dp1+r ,C2=Dp2+r$$

And the first operation was done by encrypting the private key, and we have the new key:

$$Knew = \begin{bmatrix} C1 \\ C2 \end{bmatrix};$$

Which is supposed to be sent to the receiver because even if this encrypted key is stolen, the third party attacker must decrypt the key and do not have the complete information for an algorithm GGH to decipher the encrypted key.

Third : Receiver

The Receiver recipient the encrypted private key from the sender ,and the receiver must decode the encrypted key, and in this case, use an algorithm GGH.

$$C1=[6228 \ 1097]; C2=[9708 \ 1677]$$

But the Receiver have a private key $v1=[1 \ 45]; v2=[45 \ -1];$

and also public key

$$w1=[226 \ 40]; w2=[1853 \ 319];$$

$$V = \begin{bmatrix} v1 \\ v2 \end{bmatrix}; W = \begin{bmatrix} w1 \\ w2 \end{bmatrix}$$

Use the Babai's algorithm to compute the decrypt.

$$[tnew1(1) \ tnew1(2)] = tnew1 = c1*inv(V);$$

$$Gg1 = tnew1(1)*v1 + tnew1(2)*v2$$

$$Ggh1 = Gg1* inv(W)$$

$$[tnew2(1) \ tnew2(2)] = tnew2 = c2*inv(V);$$

$$Gg2 = tnew2(1)*v1 + tnew2(2)*v2$$

$$Ggh2 = Gg2*inv(W)$$

Result of decipher of the private key encryption

$$Ggh = \begin{bmatrix} Ggh1 \\ Ggh2 \end{bmatrix}$$

VI . PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

Encryption of the important requirements of the system performance of the system speed after a safety investigation, the table (1) Includes average time it takes Windows 7 environment within Matlab R2008a to encrypt and decrypt images standard listed in the table using a program 6GB RAM processor 1.8 Ghz and Intel core quickly on a personal calculator has the following specifications in table(1).

TABLE(1)THE AVERAGE TIME TAKEN TO IMPLEMENT ENCRYPTION ALGORITHM AND DECRYPTION

Plain text	Time of encryption (sec)	Cipher text	Time of Decryption (sec)
SUPPLYFOOD	0.022179	KGMBBMFCZR	0.040974
SUPPLYFOODINLOCATION	0.022628	KGMBBMFCZRLDXOGEDADP	0.043565
SUPPLYFOODINLOCATIONILIKETHESE	0.029182	KGMBBMFCZRLDXOGEDADPFTCORZHIOE	0.045817
SUPPLYFOODINLOCATIONILIKETHESEBUTITSWELL	0.029222	KGMBBMFCZRLDXOGEDADPFTCORZHIOELYDAHYZAMZ	0.053410

VII . CONCLUSIONS

Most of the problems in the encryption and decryption are the third-party attack to steal keys, but in this paper present the bests solution to put all obstacles to the attacking party.

First, the attacker must decode the sender's encrypted private key, and then use the program Hill Cipher to decrypt the message, secondly.

But the power of the algorithm GGH became working within the algorithm Hill Cipher, and this combination of the two algorithm gave power to encrypt text messages.

We also conclude that the time required to encryption messages and decryption text messages is acceptable within real time standards. This combination of algorithm GGH and Hill Cipher are gave excellent performance, less cost and less time in executing encryption and decryption operations.

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